

Quantum Bound States and Constrained Random Walk?

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In quantum mechanics, one often speaks of wave-like behaviour. In a previous note, however, we argued that wavelike behaviour is based on “averaging” of complex, periodic probabilities and so represents an ensemble average taken at different times. If one does not want an average over different times, but rather follows a quantum particle in time, it seems it undergoes a constrained random walk. This random walk differs from usual statistical ones in that the stochastic hits from a potential must on average yield $V(x)$ at each x . We argue this is the source of the complex, periodic terms $\exp(ipx)$ which are part of a Fourier series of $V(x)$. The potential influences the momentum distribution of a particle causing it to also exhibit complex, periodic probabilities of the form $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, if one considers “or” probabilistic situations for p and $-p$, one may obtain real periodic functions such as $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$, but we argue these are time averages. A particle is either in a state p or $-p$ (or some other momentum state) at x at a particular time. Thus, the wave-like behaviour follows from averaging over time $\exp(ipx)$ terms, but at each instant it seems a particle follows a constrained random walk type motion possibly changing its direction of motion with each stochastic hit from a potential. Overall, however, there must be a periodicity in the bound system, but we have argued this (based on $\exp(iEt)$) is related to changes of a time averaged ensemble. We argue that this periodicity is also found in the constrained random walk picture if one considers a series of x_i points (x_i) with associated momenta (p_i) and uses $P(x_i)P(p_i/x_i)$ as the probability at each point. Then the average kinetic energy for a constrained random walk added to $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ yields $EW(x)W(x)$. We also argue that $W(x)W(x)$ is related to the idea of constrained random walk.

The idea of a constrained random walk in quantum mechanics has no doubt been suggested in the literature, but the main focus of quantum mechanics does not seem to be with such a random walk, but rather with averages (taken at different times) which related to a wave picture that exists only as an ensemble average.

Stochastic Potential and $\exp(ipx)$

The idea of stochastic steps or hits is common in statistics. As a result, we suggest that in quantum mechanics, a potential $V(x)$ may be an average and stochastic hits occur at each point x with certain weights. These weights (like unnormalized probabilities) are strongly influenced by the constraint that the average be $V(x)$ at each x . Thus, one may write:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } b(k,x) \quad ((1))$$

To have stochastic force hits proportional to k (momentum), $-d/dx \text{ } b(k,x)$ should be proportional to k . Thus, one may suggest:

$$b(k,x) = b(kx) \quad ((2))$$

The function b is sensitive to small x changes for large k and less sensitive for small k . One solution to ((2)) might be $b(kx) = kx$ (etc), but in such a case ((1)) would most likely not be satisfied. In fact, it seems that $b(kx) = a(k) \exp(ikx)$ is a solution to ((1)) and ((2)), but this introduces (A) periodicity and (B) complex weights which may be difficult to interpret physically. In fact, it seems complex weights are averaged for $\pm k$ in order to obtain a real function (either $\cos(kx)$ or $\sin(kx)$), but these are averages as a $+k$ hit occurs at one time and a $-k$ hit at another at the same x . Thus, the usual focus of quantum mechanics is on the wavelike $\sin(kx)$ or $\cos(kx)$ average. On average, this means that for large k , the wavelength of $\cos(kx)$ or $\sin(kx)$ is very small and the average “ k ” force is changing sign as one moves from one “hump” to another. These are average values, however, not specific random walk type motion of a quantum particle which may actually be occurring.

Constrained Random Walk Motion

In previous notes, we argued that $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Thus, there is a momentum probability distribution at x , but the probability is complex. $\sum_p P(p/x) = 1$. If a particle has momentum p at x at time t , it may receive a hit from the force of k with a weight $c(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, on average over time the force at x is: $\sum_k k c(k) \exp(kx)$ where k may be positive or negative i.e. the force hit may be in one direction or another. Thus, we suggest a particle may undergo a constrained random walk. It may be moving to the right at x , but then receive a hit and move to the left. The next hit may knock it back to the right etc. Thus, the motion is constrained random, as it is controlled by the probability distribution $P(p/x)$ which must exist at each x and includes both $\pm p$. In classical physics, one moves from an initial x to a final x sequentially in time and then back for a one dimensional bound state, but in the quantum bound case that is not the case. One may move back and forth in various patterns as long as the final probabilities are the same. $P(x)P(p/x)$ is the probability to be a x and have momentum p . $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state.

In previous notes, we argued that $W(x)W(x) = [\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)] [\sum_k a(k) \exp(ikx)]$ represents all different combinations of $a(p) \exp(ipx) a(k) \exp(ikx)$. At x , a particle may be in a momentum state p , but after a collision within Δx , it changes to $\exp(ikx)$. Thus, one has an “and” probability situation i.e. $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $a(k) \exp(ikx)$. This seems to be related to the random walk because a particle switches from moving with momentum p to moving with momentum k at x . “ p ” may be in one direction and k in the opposite. Thus, the random walk may behaviour may be responsible for the quantum spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$. It does not seem that the combined momentum $p+k$ (vectors) from $a(p) \exp(ipx) a(k) \exp(ikx)$ carries much physical meaning which is in keeping with the idea that the Fourier transform of spatial density is not particularly meaningful.

The spatial density is defined for a little interval Δx whereas $P(p/x)$ exists at a point. This leads to two kinds of averages.

Two Types of Averages

The first type of average using $P(p/x)$ represents one at point x , for example kinetic energy at x yielding energy conservation:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

The second, using $P(x)P(p/x)$, considers the probability to be at x and have a value of p . A function of p^n may be obtained from $(-i d/dx)^n$ acting on $\exp(ipx)$ so:

$$\text{Average } (p^n) = \text{Sum over } p \quad W(x) a(p) (-i d/dx)^n \exp(ipx) \text{ or } W(x) (-i d/dx)^n W(x). \quad ((4))$$

Random Walk and Cycling

A random walk sounds like it may be non-periodic, yet a bound state has periodicity represented by $\exp(iEt)$. Here t (time), however, is not the time used following a single particle as it switches momentum and position in a constrained random walk motion. Rather it measures time changes of the ensemble average.

In previous notes, we considered the idea of cycling by examining one x point and noting that ((3)) may be multiplied by $W(x)$ and then $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ written as Fourier series. In such a case:

$$p^2/2m \text{ } a(p) + \text{Sum over } k \quad V(k) a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((5))$$

There is cycling over time related to E , the average energy, but no picture of a random walk it seems. To consider a random walk, consider a set of (x_i) points occurring at times (t_i) . Then $P(x_i) P(p_i/x)$ is the probability to have a p_i at each x_i . Next, calculate the kinetic energy at each of these random walk points:

$$\text{Sum over } p_i \quad P(x_i) P(p_i/x) p_i^2/2m = -1/2m W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) \quad ((6))$$

This, added to $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ yields $E W(x)W(x)$, so it seems that the random walk is constrained in such a way that over the range of x , the average $p^2/2m$ added to the integral of $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ over dx yields E . This also seems to reinforce the idea that $W(x)W(x)$, the spatial density is related to the constrained random walk motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue a bound quantum particle undergoes a constrained random walk with different x_i and p_i values given by $P(x_i)P(p/x_i)$. We argue this random walk motion is due to hits from an average potential written as $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } b(kx)$. "b" is a function of kx so that $-d/dx$ brings out a momentum k . In order for $b(kx)$ to create $V(x)$ as an average we argue $b(kx) = c(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, one has periodicity and complex values which is somewhat unusual. We argue this gives rise to a momentum distribution at x : $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. We consider relative probabilities at x : $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and argue a particle will receive a hit from the potential knocking it into the state k with probability $a(k) \exp(ikx)$ so that one has combined relative probabilities $a(p)\exp(ipx) a(k)\exp(ikx)$. We suggest this is related to the idea of a constrained random walk. Finally, we consider a series of (x_i) points with corresponding (p_i) values as a random walk set of data. The probability to be at x_i and have p_i is $P(x_i) P(p_i/x_i)$. Writing $\text{Sum over } p_i \text{ } p_i^2/2m P(x_i)P(p_i/x_i)$ we find that when added to $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ this yields $E W(x)W(x)$ so that the constrained random walk picture leads to conservation of energy and $W(x)W(x)$ seems to be related to the random walk.